

Diazoalkanes. Part I. Reaction of Diazomethane with Methyl Ether of Cyclic Hydroxymethyleneketones

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Methyl ethers of cyclic α -hydroxymethyleneketones (β -oxoaldehydes) have been found to react with diazomethane leading to Δ^1 -pyrazolines which readily undergo elimination of nitrogen to afford β -methylated products. The latter on hydrolysis furnish α -acetylketones and it thus constitutes a simple method for the preparation of α -acetylketones from the readily accessible β -oxo-aldehydes. A convenient preparation of methyl ether of hydroxymethyleneketones and their probable configuration have also been described. A preliminary account has already been published¹.

It is well-known² that diazomethane reacts with a variety of compounds containing activated double bond, e. g., α , β -unsaturated ketones, aldehydes, and esters with the formation of pyrazoline derivatives. The initial product is a Δ^1 -pyrazoline (I) which subsequently rearranges to more stable Δ^2 -pyrazoline (II) if by so doing a conjugated system results:

It is further known that pyrazolines of the type (I & II), unsubstituted on nitrogen yield methylated olefins (III) together with varying amounts of cyclopropane derivatives when heated or brought into contact with suitable catalysts. A few examples of α , β -unsaturated ketones or esters thus undergoing β -methylation through the intermediacy of pyrazolines are recorded in the literature³⁻⁷. To these we now add a new series of compounds, the methyl ethers of cyclic α -hydroxymethyleneketones which react with diazomethane in a similar fashion.

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Hydroxymethyleneketones are readily available by acylation of ketones with esters of formic acid⁸. They react with diazomethane often sluggishly but readily in presence of methanol⁹ to furnish a stereoisomeric mixture of O-alkylated products. These methyl ethers contain an α, β -unsaturated ketonic system and in principle can react with a second molecule of diazomethane to afford pyrazolines. No such reaction has, however, been reported in the literature to our knowledge and we undertook to investigate. Methyl ether of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-tetralone¹⁰ was selected as a model compound for study, because of its ready availability and crystalline nature. One of its isomers, possibly the trans one (IV), m. p. 62-63° (*vide infra*) was obtained by treatment of the hydroxymethyleneketone with dimethyl sulphate and alkali. The structure was confirmed by its NMR spectrum consisting of a pair of doublets (1 H) at 1.65 T (C_8H), a singlet (1 H) at 2.15 T ($=CHOMe$), an irregular multiplet (3 H) centred at 2.35 T (aromatic H's), a sharp singlet (3 H) at 5.98 T ($-OCH_3$) and a broad peak (4 H) at 7.05 T ($-CH_2CH_2-$). This was treated

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

with an excess of an ethereal solution of diazomethane at room temperature for several hours. The product, a yellow viscous oil, obtained after evaporation of ether in the cold, was found to contain 92% of the pyrazolone (V), ν_{max} 1602 cm^{-1} (strong, $-N=N-$), on the basis of nitrogen estimation. It decomposed slowly at room temperature but readily on warming and, on slow distillation, afforded a crystalline enol ether (VI), m. p. 75° in high yield. The structure of the compound followed from its NMR spectrum: multiplets at 1.65 T (1 H) and 2.35 T (3 H) (aromatic H's), singlet (3 H) at 6.10 T ($-OCH_3$), a broad peak (4 H) at 7.10 T (methylenes) and a sharp singlet (3 H) at 7.35 T ($-CH_3$). A comparison of the spectrum with that of 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (IV) showed that the peak of the vinyl proton at 2.15 T in the latter has been replaced by a methyl peak

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at 7.35 τ in the former. The structure was further confirmed by its hydrolysis to 2-acetyl-1-tetralone¹¹, m.p. and mixed m.p. 55-56°, an authentic specimen of which was prepared according to known procedure¹². Copper derivative, m.p. 207° and IR spectra of the two diketones were identical. The same enol ether (VI) was obtained, albeit in low yield, when the hydroxymethyleneketone was treated with an excess of diazomethane.

It is thus established that the enol ethers of the type (IV) react with diazomethane, like other α , β -unsaturated ketones, to furnish Δ^1 -pyrazolines. These then eliminate nitrogen either in a concerted process shown in diagram (V) or through fission of C—N bond giving rise to an intermediate resonance stabilised diazanium betaine¹³ (VII). A small amount of cyclopropane derivative might be formed as a bye-product, but this was not detected in the present experiments. The ease of nitrogen elimination is evidently due to the fact that the less stable Δ^1 -pyrazoline (V) does not easily isomerise to Δ^2 -pyrazoline, which in this case can not form any conjugated system. Moreover, the methoxyl group at β -carbon probably facilitates the hydride transfer by mesomeric effect. A number of compounds similar to the enol ether (IV) but with aryl group in the place of methoxyl, on the other hand, have recently been shown¹⁴ to give quite stable spiro- Δ^2 -pyrazolines on treatment with diazomethane.

The methyl ethers of hydroxymethylene derivatives of a few more ketones such as cyclohexanone, cyclopentanone, and 1-hydrindanone were likewise treated with diazomethane. In each case the intermediate pyrazoline derivative was isolated, characterised by IR spectrum and nitrogen estimation, and decomposed into corresponding methylated product by heating. The yield was uniformly good (>80%) and the products were identified by hydrolysis to 2-acetylketones and comparison of the latter with authentic specimens. The pyrazoline from 2-methoxymethylenecyclohexan-1-one was very unstable eliminating nitrogen visibly at room temperature. The methyl ether of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-hydrindanone was a crystalline solid, m.p. 101°, as also its β -methylated product (as VI), m.p. 125°, obtained after diazomethane treatment and decomposition. The NMR spectra of these two compounds were in perfect agreement with the structures (*vide* experimental). The β -proton in the former was however buried among the aromatic protons and was replaced by a methyl peak at 7.55 τ in the latter.

The reaction thus seems to be a general one for cyclic methoxymethyleneketones. One notable exception was the methyl ether of 3-hydroxymethylene-camphor¹⁵, which did not afford any pyrazoline derivative under the usual condition. The failure in this case may be ascribed to the steric strain involved in the formation of the spiro-pyrazoline. Preliminary experiments with methyl ethers of acyclic hydroxymethyleneketones showed that they react with diazomethane slowly and incompletely. A full account of these experiments will appear at a later publication. The methyl ether of pentan-2, 4-dione (acetylacetone) (VIII)^{9, 16} also did not form any pyrazolino derivative. Apparently, the presence of a β -proton is essential for the addition of diazomethane to take place.

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The method where applicable affords a convenient route to α -acetylketones from easily accessible β -oxo-aldehydes and may be particularly useful for the preparation of enol ethers of the type (VI) which are difficult to obtain otherwise in pure state. 2-Acetyl-1-tetralone, for example, on methylation yielded a liquid, possibly a mixture of isomeric (both structurally and geometrically) enol ethers as shown by thin layer chromatography.

There are several methods available for the preparation of enol ethers from hydroxymethyleneketones. Treatment with diazomethane either alone or in presence of methanol as catalyst, though simple, leads to a mixture of *cis* and *trans* ethers evidently through a kinetically controlled process, and is further complicated by the possibility of pyrazoline formation from the resultant enol ether. Heating the hydroxymethyleneketones with methanol-*p*-toluenesulphonic acid and separation of water as an azeotropic mixture with benzene are common procedure. The process is a thermodynamically controlled one and the product is therefore expected to be the more stable *trans* ether. However, the method when applied to 2-hydroxymethylene-1-tetralone afforded the desired methyl ether in very poor yield along with some tetralone. There was no separation of water and the low yield was presumably due to a retro-Claisen reaction leading to 1-tetralone and formic acid or methyl formate depending on whether water or methanol took part in the cleavage reaction. Other methods include treatment of hydroxymethyleneketones with methyl iodide or dimethyl sulphate in presence of base⁷. The use of methyl iodide generally leads to considerable C-alkylation and finally dimethyl sulphate and anhydrous potassium carbonate in boiling acetone was found to be the method of choice. The reaction is in all probability a kinetically controlled one and in view of the bulky nature of dimethyl sulphate, the product was expected to be predominantly *trans* with respect to the orientations of C=O and -OMe. It was indeed found that the methyl ethers formed in all cases were homogeneous (thin layer chromatography) and probably had the *trans* configuration (as IV). This view was substantiated to some extent by the fact that the methyl ether of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-tetralone prepared by this procedure was found to be identical with that obtained by methanol-*p*-toluenesulphonic acid method. Moreover, acetylacetone when methylated with dimethyl sulphate under the same condition afforded a pure methyl ether which compared well with the *trans* isomer (VIII)^{8,18} with respect to its boiling point and refractive index.

Finally, the NMR spectrum of the methyl ether (IV) shows the methine proton (=CHOMe) at a considerably low field (2.15 *T*). This is more consistent with the *S-cis* configuration (IV)¹⁹ where the carbonyl group can cause maximum deshielding of the β -proton. However, the position of this methine proton depends very much on the over-all structure of the enol ethers, see for example, 2-methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone where this proton is buried among aromatic protons somewhere at 2.95 *T*, and 3-methoxymethylenecamphor²⁰ where this appears at 3.25 *T*. In absence of the NMR spectrum of the other isomer, therefore, this evidence is not conclusive.

The configuration of the pyrazoline (V) and the methylated ether (VI) is based on the generally accepted² *cis* addition of diazomethane to a double bond. The *trans*

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configuration in these compounds are also to be expected from the consideration of the Coulombic repulsion forces between the lone pair of electrons of methoxyl oxygen and the π -cloud of the carbonyl group and the greater steric requirement of the former. If the reaction is considered to proceed via the betaine (VII), the latter would assume a configuration in which the two groups would be furthest separated. In either case, a collapse to the trans enol ether (VI) is most logical.

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s are corrected. The NMR spectra were measured on a Varian A60 spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal reference and deuteriochloroform as solvent. Petroleum indicates a fraction, b.p. 40-60°. The IR spectra of the liquids were taken neat and of the solids in chloroform solutions. All UV spectra were measured in absolute ethanol.

A. Preparation of Methyl Ethers of Hydroxymethyleneketones.

2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (IV).—(a) *Dimethyl Sulphate Method.*—A mixture of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-tetralone¹⁰ (10.8 g.), purified dimethyl sulphate (10.8 ml.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (21.6 g.), and dry acetone (130 ml.) was refluxed, on the water bath for 11-12 hr. The solvent was removed at the water pump, the residue diluted with water, and organic matter taken up in ether. The ethereal extract was once washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and the solvent evaporated. The residue on distillation afforded 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (IV) as a pale yellow solid (10.4 g., 96%), b.p. 140-150°/2 mm, m.p. 52-55°. It crystallised from petroleum in colourless prisms (8.0 g.), m.p. 62-63° (Found: C, 76.4; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.0; H, 6.4%); λ_{max} 264 (log ϵ 3.94) and 295 μ (log ϵ 4.06).

(b) *Methanol-p-Toluenesulphonic Acid Method.*—2-Hydroxymethylene-1-tetralone (11.6 g.), methanol (8 ml.), dry benzene (120 ml.), and p-toluenesulphonic acid (260 mg.) were refluxed on the water bath for 7-8 hr. using a Dean and Stark water separator. No water was however separated. The cooled solution was poured into an ice-cold saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate. The benzene layer was separated, washed thoroughly with cold aqueous 4% sodium hydroxide solution, then with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and solvent evaporated. The residue was distilled in vacuo and two fractions were collected. The lower boiling fraction (1.1 g.), b.p. 100-120°/2 mm. was mainly 1-tetralone as evidenced by the formation of a dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. 255°. The higher boiling fraction (2.5 g.), b.p. 130-145°/2 mm. solidified on cooling and crystallised from petroleum in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 63°. The m.p. was not depressed when admixed with 2-methoxymethylene-1-tetralone prepared by method (a).

2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone.—2-Hydroxymethylene-1-hydrindanone, m.p. 112° was prepared according to Johnson and Shelberg¹⁰. A mixture of the hydroxymethylene compound (11.6 g.), anhydrous potassium carbonate (30 g.), dimethyl sulphate (15 ml.), and acetone (160 ml.) was refluxed and the product worked up as before. 2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone was obtained as a yellow solid (12.0 g.), b.p. 155°/1 mm, m.p. 88-90°, which crystallised from benzene-petroleum in yellow plates (7.8 g.), m.p. 101° (Found: C, 75.5; H, 6.05. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 75.9; H, 5.75%). The NMR spectrum had the following peaks: multiplets centred at 2.61 τ (1H) and at 2.95 τ (4 H) (aromatic H's and

=CHOMe), a sharp singlet (3 H) at 6.3 τ (-OCH₃), and a singlet (2 H) at 6.59 τ (-CH₂-). The compound turned brown slowly on keeping.

2-Methoxymethylenecyclohexan-1-one. — 2-Methoxymethylenecyclohexan-1-one was likewise prepared from 2-hydroxymethylenecyclohexan-1-one²¹ (11.6 g.), dimethyl sulphate (16.2 ml.), potassium carbonate (32.5 g.), and acetone (195 ml.). The methyl ether was obtained as a colourless oil (9.5 g.), b.p. 105-110°/10 mm (Found: C, 68.4; H, 8.5. C₈H₁₄O₂ requires C, 68.6; H, 8.6%).

2-Methoxymethylenecyclopentan-1-one. — 2-Hydroxymethylenecyclopentan-1-one¹⁰ was similarly converted into the methyl ether, b.p. 110°/15 mm (Found: C, 66.8; H, 8.1. C₇H₁₀O₂ requires C, 66.7; H, 7.9%).

3-Methoxymethylenecamphor. — 3-Hydroxymethylenecamphor (8.4 g.), prepared from (+) camphor according to the procedure of Organic Reactions⁸, was heated with a mixture of dimethyl sulphate (8.2 ml.), potassium carbonate (16.2 g.), and acetone (160 ml.) on the water bath for 10 hr. The methyl ether thus obtained was a viscous liquid (6.4 g.), b.p. 102-103°/1 mm; n_D^{20} 1.5038; and $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 188.1$ (c 4, EtOH) (Found: C, 74.1; H, 9.4. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₈O₂: C, 74.2; H, 9.4%). Reported²² $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 201.6$.

4-Methoxy-pent-3-en-2-one. (VIII). — (a) A mixture of pentan-2, 4-dione (15.6 g.), b.p. 135-136°, dimethyl sulphate (27.0 ml.), potassium carbonate (54.0 g.), and acetone (26.0 ml.) was refluxed for 12 hr. on the water bath. The product was worked up in the usual way and distilled to a colourless oil (7.0 g.), b.p.: 62°/12 mm, 72°/15 mm, and 105°/755 mm; n_D^{20} 1.4548; λ_{max} 250 μ (ϵ 10580). The reported data⁹ for the trans isomer, b.p. 61-62°/10-11 mm.

(b) Pentan-2, 4-dione (6 g.) in ether (20 ml.) was mixed with an ethereal solution of diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethyl urea²³ (20 g.). Methanol (4 ml.) was added and the mixture left overnight at room temperature. Ether was then removed and the residue carefully fractionated under reduced pressure. After a little fore-run of the trans isomer (0.5 g.), b.p. 60-80°/11 mm, the cis methyl ether was collected as a colourless oil (3.5 g.), b.p. 90°/11 mm; reported⁹ b.p. 84-86°/10 mm. It has n_D^{20} 1.4813; λ_{max} 255 μ (ϵ 16190). The methyl ether on distillation under atmospheric pressure was partially converted into trans isomer, the major portion boiling at 170°. The distilled product had n_D^{20} 1.4648 showing it as a mixture of cis and trans isomers.

B. Treatment of the α -Methoxymethylene ketones with Diazomethane.

General Procedure. A solution of the α methoxymethylene ketone (0.1 mole) dissolved in minimum quantity of anhydrous ether was kept in with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (0.3 mole) prepared from nitrosomethylurea, at room temperature for 20-30 hr. The solution was filtered off from the polymethylene compounds and slowly evaporated under reduced pressure without any external heating. The yellow-red oil thus obtained was dried at room temperature under vacuum and analysed for nitrogen. The percentages of nitrogen varied from 80 to 92% of theory based on the structure of the corresponding pyrazoline. Some of these compounds started losing nitrogen at room temperature and gave a low nitrogen percentage.

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22. A. I. Vogel, "A Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 967. Longmans, London (1962).

The crude pyrazoline derivative was at first gently heated with the tip of a flame when evolution of nitrogen became visible. The reaction soon grew vigorous and the flame was removed. The dark liquid left after elimination of nitrogen was then slowly distilled in vacuum. The solids were purified by crystallisation while the liquids were redistilled. The following compounds were prepared:

2- α -Methoxyethylidene-1-tetralone (VI).—(a) 2-Methoxymethylene-1-tetralone (IV) (4.7 g.) was treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethyl urea (12.6 g.) and ether (120 ml.). The pyrazoline (5.4 g.) had λ_{max} 253 (ϵ 10800) and 296 $\mu\mu$ (ϵ 3817); ν_{max} 1670 cm^{-1} (strong) and 1602 cm^{-1} (fairly strong). This was decomposed and distilled as described above to furnish 2- α -methoxyethylidene-1-tetralone (VI) (4.0 g.), b.p. 160-165°/5 mm, m.p. 65-68°. It was crystallised from petroleum in pale yellow plates, m.p. 75° (Found: C, 77.1; H, 6.9. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.2; H, 6.9%; λ_{max} 261 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.86) and 316 $\mu\mu$. ($\log \epsilon$ 4.07).

(b) A solution of 2-hydroxymethylene-1-tetralone (10 g.) was treated similarly with diazomethane. A viscous oil (7.8 g.), b.p. 140-150°/2 mm. was obtained which on keeping in the refrigerator, deposited solid (1.5 g.). This was filtered and crystallised from petroleum in yellow plates, m.p. 73-75°. The m.p. was not depressed by admixture with a sample prepared by method (a).

2- α -Methoxyethylidene-1-hydrindanone.—2-Methoxymethylene-1-hydrindanone (5 g.) dissolved in tetrahydrofuran (20 ml.) was kept in with diazomethane. The crude pyrazoline (6.0 g.), ν_{max} 1710 and 1615 cm^{-1} , afforded 2- α -methoxyethylidene-1-hydrindanone (4.8 g.), b.p. 150-155°/0.5 mm. It crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 125° (Found: C 76.4; H, 6.7. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 76.6; H, 6.4%).

2- α -Methoxyethylidenecyclohexan-1-one.—2-Methoxymethylenecyclohexan-1-one (7.0 g.) afforded the crude pyrazoline (9.0 g.) which lost nitrogen spontaneously at room temperature. It had λ_{max} 249 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.18) and 280 $\mu\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.35); ν_{max} 1702 and 1614 cm^{-1} ; and was converted by distillation into 2- α -methoxyethylidenecyclohexan-1-one (5.5 g.), b.p. 110-115°/10 mm (Found: C, 70.5; H, 9.7. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 70.1; H, 9.1%). This was a pale yellow liquid with a characteristic odour.

2- α -Methoxyethylidenecyclopentan-1-one.—2-Methoxymethylenecyclopentan-1-one (3.2 g.) similarly afforded 2- α -methoxyethylidenecyclopentan-1-one (3.0 g.), b.p. 110-115°/14 mm. as a pale yellow liquid (Found: C, 68.0; H, 8.7. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 68.6; H, 8.6%).

3-Methoxymethylenecamphor and 4-Methoxy-pent-3-en-2-one (VIII) were likewise treated with diazomethane. But the product on removal of ether was found not to contain any nitrogen and on distillation yielded the original compounds as shown by IR spectra.

C. Preparation of α -Acetylketones.

(a) *By Hydrolysis of 2- α -Methoxyethylideneketones.*—In a typical experiment, 2- α -methoxyethylidene-1-tetralone (VI) (0.9 g.) was dissolved in methanol (5 ml.) and water (0.5 ml.), cooled in ice, and concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.2 ml.) was added to it. The mixture was kept at 0° for 24 hr., diluted with water, and the organic matter taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was extracted with 5% aqueous potassium hydroxide (2×15 ml.) and the yellow alkali solution carefully acidified. 2-Acetyl-1-tetralone (0.65 g.) was obtained in glistening white plates which was crystallised from methanol

and had m.p. 55-56°; reported¹¹ m.p. 55-56°. The m.p. was not depressed on admixture with an authentic specimen. The diketone afforded a greyish green copper derivative, m.p. and mixed m.p. 207-208°

2-Acetylcyclohexan-1-one²³, b.p. 110°/18 mm, copper-derivative, m.p. 161-163°; 2-acetyl-1-hydrindanone, m.p. 81°, copper-derivative, m.p. 265° (decomp.); 2-acetylcyclopentan-1-one²⁴, b.p. 85-90°/15 mm were obtained in a similar way from the corresponding 2- α -methoxyethylideneketones. Their identities were established by mixed m.p. determination where possible and comparison of IR spectra of authentic specimens (*vide infra*).

(b) *Synthesis of Acetylketones from Ketones*.—For the preparation of authentic α -acetylketones, the general method described in Organic Reactions²⁵ was adopted. In a typical experiment, sodium hydride (4.8 g., 50% dispersed in oil, 0.1 mole) and ethyl acetate (8.8 g., 0.1 mole) were kept stirring under nitrogen. Few drops of methanol were added to initiate the reaction and 1-tetralone (7.3 g., 0.05 mole) in ether (15 ml.) was introduced drop-wise during 30-40 min. The mixture was then warmed at 40-50° for about 3 hr. The resultant solid mass was cooled in ice and slowly decomposed by addition of cold water. The aqueous alkaline layer was separated from the ether and carefully acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid to liberate 2-acetyl-1-tetralone as a solid. It was extracted with ether, ethereal solution dried (Na₂SO₄) and distilled to furnish a crystalline solid (7.5 g.) b.p. 155-158°/10 mm. It crystallised from methanol in white glistening plates, m.p. 56-57° (Found: C, 76.5; H, 6.6. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₄O₂: C, 76.6; H, 6.4%).

2-Acetyl-1-hydrindanone was obtained by this method but in very poor yield (32%). It crystallised from methanol in light yellow prisms, m.p. 81° (Found: C, 75.4; H, 5.8. C₁₇H₁₄O₂ requires C, 75.9; H, 5.75%).

Other acetylketones mentioned in this paper were obtained by this method in quite good yield.

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